

Original Article

Smart Quercetin Delivery: Tailored Sodium Alginate Microbeads for Enhanced Antioxidant and Controlled Degradation

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Quercetin (Qur), a natural flavonoid exhibiting significant antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer effects, encounters constraints in clinical use owing to inadequate solubility, diminished bioavailability, and fast metabolism. To address these problems, sodium alginate (Na-Algn), which is biocompatible and biodegradable, has emerged as a viable medium for Qur delivery. This study aims to design and optimize the Qur-loaded Na-Alg microbead carriers, examining the impact of different calcium chloride concentrations on cross-linking density and release patterns of the therapeutic agent. Change of cross-linker and Na-Algn alters the drug encapsulation efficiency (EE %). This approach improves the bioavailability of quercetin and stability by utilizing the interaction between Qur, calcium ions, and the alginate matrix, hence extending its therapeutic effects. The degradation, morphological, antioxidant, and *in vitro* drug release findings indicate that Na-Algn beads serve as versatile and effective vehicles for drug administration, positioning them as attractive options for enhancing the clinical efficacy of bioactive therapeutic agents.

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Introduction

Quercetin (Qur), a natural flavonoid present in various fruits and vegetables, has attracted much interest for its powerful antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer characteristics [1-3]. Despite its medicinal potential, sodium alginate (Na-Algn), a biocompatible and biodegradable polymer, is capable of encapsulating bioactive chemicals and releasing them in a controlled manner. The Na-Alg structure, including alternating blocks of β -D-mannuronic acid (M) and α -L-guluronic acid (G), facilitates the creation of microbeads upon cross-linking with divalent cations such as calcium [4,5]. Na-Algn has emerged as a promising medium for drug delivery usage, capable of encapsulating a diverse array of medicinal agents, including small compounds, proteins, and

peptides. The creation of Qur-loaded Na-Algn carriers is essential for improving drug delivery systems that augment the therapeutic efficacy of bioactive compounds. Enhancing the solubility and bioavailability of quercetin using drug carriers could augment its clinical use and facilitate prolonged release, hence minimizing the necessity for frequent dosage and enhancing patient adherence [6,7].

A crucial aspect of Na-Algn for medication administration is its regulated breakdown rate. The degradation of the matrix directly affects the release kinetics of the encapsulated drug, rendering it a crucial element for optimizing effective drug delivery [8]. By adjusting variables such as calcium chloride content, cross-linking density, and the inclusion of additional biopolymers, the degradation of Na-Algn carriers may be precisely regulated, rendering them very suitable for sustained drug release. Controlled degradation facilitates a continuous and timed release of medicinal substances, proving especially beneficial in the management of chronic diseases, cancer treatment, and tissue regeneration. In diabetes care, insulin-loaded Na-Algn beads facilitate a regulated

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release of insulin, hence reducing the necessity for frequent injections [9]. In cancer therapy, Na-Algn beads can be designed to deliver chemotherapeutic medications specifically to the tumor location, minimizing systemic toxicity and improving therapeutic effectiveness [10].

Ke et al. developed Algn-gelatin core-shell capsules to enhance the proliferation of human osteoblast-like MG-63 cells in three-dimensional culture, leading to increased osteogenic gene markers [11]. To improve the release properties of the delivery system, the integration of two or more matrices to form a composite vehicle offers a superior method that can alleviate the constraints linked to a single material. Composite gel beads composed of micelles and Na-Algn were made using a Na-Algn matrix, with indomethacin (IND) enclosed within micelles formed from a six-arm block copolymer, poly(α -caprolactone)-block-(dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate (S(PCL-b-PDMA)₆). The release of IND from micelles, Na-Algn beads, and micelles/Na-Algn beads have shown significant variability under acidic and neutral pH conditions, suggesting that the beads protect IND from release in acidic stomach environments while enabling targeted delivery to the small intestine and colon. The release behavior of the micelles/Na-Algn beads was influenced by the concentrations of sodium alginate and calcium chloride, due to variations in crosslinking density [12]. The objective of this research is to develop and optimize quercetin-loaded sodium alginate drug carriers using calcium chloride as a cross-linker. Additionally, the study aims to explore how varying the concentration of calcium chloride affects the crosslinking density and drug release profile, with the ultimate goal of creating a highly efficient drug delivery system with improved anti-oxidant property.

Materials and Methods

Sodium alginate –LV extrapure (Sigma Aldrich) and calcium chloride (CaCl₂, SRL) were procured in India. Quercetin and Dialysis membrane-60 (LA390-1MT) was sourced from Sigma Aldrich and Himedia (India) respectively.

Development of quercetin (Qur) loaded sodium alginate beads

Na-Algn microbeads were prepared using CaCl₂ as cross-linker. For the preparation of Na-Algn microbeads, 50 ml of aqueous polymer solution was prepared. On the other hand, 100 ml of CaCl₂ was prepared. The polymer solution was subsequently introduced into the CaCl₂ solution in a drop-wise manner using a 10 ml hypodermic syringe and needle #21G, while the mixture was maintained at room temperature and stirred continuously. The beads, which were subsequently formed, were cured in the CaCl₂ solution for 1 hour, rinsed with distilled water, and allowed to dry at room temperature until they were completely dry [13]. For Qur loading, Qur solution (10 mg) was added to the Na-Alg polymer solution. Then, the same procedure was followed to obtain Qur loaded Na-Algn microbeads formation. In this study, varying ratios of Na-Algn to CaCl₂ concentrations were used to attain the

microbeads with minimal degradation rate and which is listed in table 1. The best sample was chosen based on its higher encapsulation efficiency (EE%), which was subjected to further analyses (2Ca-2Algn). The Qur loaded 2Ca-2Algn microbeads were designated as Qur@2Ca-2Algn.

Materials characterization

Functional group analysis was performed using Fourier Transform Infra-red Spectroscopy (FTIR) using Alpha II (Bruker), Germany. Morphology of the microbeads was observed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) from SIGMA HV – Carl Zeiss (Germany).

Drug encapsulation analysis

To quantify the percentage of encapsulation efficacy (EE %) of the prepared beads, an indirect method was employed. Briefly, the beads were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes, and the resulting supernatant was employed to evaluate the EE %. An ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (JASCO V-730 spectrophotometer) was employed to measure the absorbance of Qur at 375 nm [14]. The provided formula was employed to determine the drug input rate and the percentage of drug encapsulation efficiency.

$$EE (\%) = \frac{\text{Total Drug} - \text{Free Drug}}{\text{Total Drug}} \times 100$$

Degradation behaviour

The degradation behavior of the Algn nanoparticles was investigated in PBS (pH 7.4). In triplicate, 50 mg of samples were immersed in PBS for varying durations, including 1, 3, and 5 days, at ambient temperature ($\pm 37^\circ\text{C}$). The initial weight of the beads was denoted as W_0 . The beads were extracted from the PBS and washed with double distilled water after soaking for varying durations. The dry weight of the beads was recorded as W_t after drying [15]. The degradation rate of the beads was determined using the subsequent equation:

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} \text{ degradation} = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0} \times 100$$

DPPH radical scavenging assay

The efficacy of the microbeads to scavenge free radicals was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay [16]. The capacity of the microbeads to donate hydrogen atoms was assessed through the decolorization of a methanol solution of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). In the presence of antioxidants, DPPH produces violet/purple color in methanol solution and dissipates to yellow shades. A 0.1 mM DPPH solution in methanol was prepared, and 2.4 mL of this solution was combined with 1.6 mL of a methanolic solution of the microbeads at varying concentrations (10 to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The reaction mixture was vortexed extensively and maintained at ambient temperature in the absence of light for 30 minutes. The absorbance of the mixture was determined by spectrophotometry at 517 nm. The control was a DPPH solution containing 1.6 mL of methanolic solution without samples. The following equation was used to determine the percentage of DPPH radical scavenging activity:

$$\% \text{ DPPH radical scavenging activity} = \frac{(A_0 - A_1)}{A_0} \times 100$$

Where, the absorbance of the control is A_0 , and the absorbance of the sample is A_1 .

In vitro drug release behaviour

The *in vitro* Qur release behavior was analyzed using the dialysis bag technique. The drug release was conducted in pH condition, 7.4 with PBS serving as the medium. The dialysis bag was filled with 50 mg of Qur-loaded beads and the ends were securely tied.

Table 1: Concentration of Na-Algn and CaCl₂

S. No.	Na-Algn (wt %)	CaCl ₂ (wt %)	Sample code	EE%
1	1	1	1Ca-1Algn	18.34 \pm 4.34
2	1	1.5	1Ca-1.5Algn	21.56 \pm 6.12
3	1	2	1Ca-2Algn	49.67 \pm 5.89
4	2	1	2Ca-1Algn	25.87 \pm 4.89
5	2	1.5	2Ca-1.5Algn	42.87 \pm 6.45
6	2	2	2Ca-2Algn	62.76 \pm 5.14

The bag was then placed in a screw-capped container containing 50 ml of PBS and maintained at 37°C under a modest shaking condition. At each predetermined time interval, 3 ml of PBS was withdrawn for quantification and replaced with a new 3 ml of PBS. The UV-Visible spectrophotometer was employed to determine the cumulative quantity of drug release percentage at 375 nm [14].

Statistical analysis

All the samples were investigated in triplicates ($n = 3$) and obtained results were expressed in mean \pm SD (standard deviation). The data were analyzed using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Functional group analysis

The FTIR spectrum (figure 1) of pure sodium alginate typically shows characteristic peaks at 3252 cm^{-1} due to O-H stretching, and 1624 cm^{-1} for asymmetric stretching of carboxylate groups ($-\text{COO}^-$). The peaks at 2945 cm^{-1} and 1409 cm^{-1} , are related to (C-H) stretching vibration and symmetric stretching of the carboxyl group (COO^-), respectively. The peak at 1109 cm^{-1} attributed to (C-O) stretching of vibrations, which are characteristic of the glycosidic linkages in the polysaccharide backbone of alginate. FTIR peaks between sodium alginate and calcium chloride cross-linked alginate lies in the shifts and changes in intensity associated with the carboxylate groups ($-\text{COO}^-$) and hydroxyl (O-H) groups. When calcium chloride is added, the interaction between calcium ions (Ca^{2+}) and the carboxylate groups of alginate causes the carboxyl group peak to shift to a lower wavenumber (around 1585 cm^{-1}), indicating ionic crosslinking between calcium and alginate. The broad O-H stretching peak around 3273 cm^{-1} in sodium alginate become reduced after crosslinking due to changes in hydrogen bonding and interactions between calcium and the hydroxyl groups. Quercetin has characteristic FTIR peaks, such as C=O stretching around 1650-

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of Na-Alg, and Qur loaded Alg beads

1600 cm^{-1} (from the flavonoid structure) [17]. Because of this, a slight peak shift might be observed to lower wavenumber due to interactions between the quercetin molecules and the alginate matrix, particularly with calcium ions and the carboxylate groups of alginate [18].

Morphological analysis of sodium alginate beads

In order to examine the surface morphology of Na-Alg microbeads, surface FESEM analysis was performed. Figures 2(A) and 2(B), presents the topographical images of pure Algn beads,

Figure 2: FESEM micrographs of pure Na-Algn microbeads (A) & (B) and Qur loaded Na-Algn microbeads (C) & (D); Whereas photographical representation of as-prepared Algn (E) & Qur loaded Na-Algn microbeads (G) and dried Algn (F) & Qur loaded Algn microbeads (H)

Figure 3: DPPH radical scavenging activity of pure Algn and Qur@2Ca-2Algn microbeads

Figure 4: Degradation rate of Na-Algn beads with respect to CaCl₂ cross-linking

and Qur loaded 2Ca-2Algn beads (figures 2(C) and 2(D)). Pure and Qur loaded Algn microbeads shows spherical, and smooth surfaces. The spherical shape of pure Na-Algn beads indicates efficient crosslinking, often resulting in smooth surfaces and uniform morphology. For drug-loaded beads, also exhibits spherical beads suggest successful drug incorporation into the alginate matrix.

Antioxidant study

DPPH radical scavenging activity is shown in figure 3. Pure Na-Algn shows minimal antioxidant activity, with only 9% inhibition at the highest concentration (100 µg/mL), indicating its weak free radical scavenging potential. Qur@2Ca-2Algn exhibits significantly higher DPPH scavenging activity compared to pure Na-Algn,

reaching 42% inhibition at 100 µg/mL dosage, due to the antioxidant property of Qur. The gradual increase in inhibition with Qur@Ca-Algn suggests a controlled release of quercetin from the alginate matrix, providing moderate but sustained antioxidant activity. The comparison highlights that sodium alginate alone is not a potent antioxidant, but its ability to carry and release bioactive compounds like Qur enhances its functionality. Pure alginate possesses low antioxidant activity that can be attributed to its polysaccharide nature, which lacks active antioxidant groups [19]. The encapsulation of Qur within the alginate matrix provides a practical means for sustained antioxidant delivery of Qur@2Ca-2Algn microbeads. The enhanced performance of Qur@2Ca-2Algn compared to pure alginate demonstrates the potential of alginate-based systems for functional applications. Overall, the results emphasize the value of loading alginate with active antioxidants, enhancing its performance

Figure 5: FESEM micrographs of pure Algn microbeads (a) to (c) and Qur loaded Algn microbeads (d) to (f) after 5 days of *in vitro* degradation

Figure 6: Qur release profile from Ca-Alg microbead carriers

beyond its primary role as a biopolymer carrier [20].

Degradation behaviour of Na-Alg microbeads

The degradation data (figure 4) of Na-Alg beads over 5 days shows that 1Ca-1Alg has the highest degradation rate, starting at 25.57% on day 1 and reaching 47.57% by day 5, indicating its potential for fast drug release. 1Ca-1.5Alg follows a similar trend but with a slower start, reaching 45.78%, suggesting moderate control over degradation. 1Ca-2Alg degrades more slowly, starting at 18.54% and ending at 37.54%, whereas, 2Ca-1Alg shows a balanced degradation profile, rising from 23.67% to 39.67%. 2Ca-1.5Alg follows a moderate degradation path, reaching 42.45%. The beads formed from 2Ca-2Alg degrade the slowest, from 15.93% to 37.93%, making it a potential candidate for applications requiring longer-term stability. Among these, the slower-degrading formulation (i.e. 2Ca-2Alg) is better suited for sustained release or structural support in wound healing. When incorporation of Qur into 2Ca-2Alg (Qur@2Ca-2Alg), the degradation rate was slightly increased compared to blank 2Ca-2Alg beads. From the degradation results, the microbeads 2Ca-2Alg and Qur@2Ca-2Alg were considered for further studies owing to its lowered degradation with enhanced stability. Overall, this degradation data provides valuable insights for tailoring the alginate formulations to specific biomedical applications based on desired release profiles and structural longevity [21].

After degradation, FESEM analysis was carried out to analyze the morphology of the microbeads and shown in figure 5. Pure Na-Alg typically loses their spherical shape, developing pores or several cracks due to polymer breakdown. Drug-loaded beads may degrade differently, with drug interactions either slowing or accelerating the degradation process. Increased porosity and structural fragmentation in both cases highlight the progressive breakdown of the alginate network [12]. For Qur-loaded beads, these changes facilitate drug release, with the degradation pattern directly impacting the release rate. The study of post-degradation morphology provides insights into the stability of the beads and their potential for controlled drug delivery. Ultimately, observing these changes helps in understanding the effectiveness of Na-Alg beads as drug delivery systems.

Drug release profile of Qur from Ca-Alg microbeads

Free quercetin shows a rapid release within the first 3 hours, reaching around 80%, which is characteristic of non-encapsulated drugs dissolving quickly in the medium (figure 6). The quercetin-loaded alginate microbeads (Qur@2Ca-2Alg) show a much slower and controlled release, reaching around 40% at 3 hours and gradually increasing over time. Free quercetin reaches nearly 90% cumulative release by 6 hours, indicating that it is fully released into the medium in a short period. In contrast, quercetin from the alginate beads continues releasing at a slower rate, reaching around 70% at 24 hours and plateauing near 80% after 36 hours, demonstrating sustained release. The slower release from Qur@2Ca-2Alg indicates that the encapsulation within calcium-alginate helps in controlling the drug release, which can prevent burst release and maintain therapeutic levels over an extended period. The slower release of quercetin from alginate beads could provide longer-lasting antioxidant or therapeutic effects compared to the rapid clearance of free quercetin. Encapsulation may protect quercetin from environmental degradation, which can be crucial for maintaining its bioactivity over extended periods [22]. The encapsulation of Qur in sodium alginate microbeads is effective in controlling the release rate, making it a promising strategy for sustained drug delivery systems, especially for compounds like Qur with low bioavailability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, sodium alginate beads with controlled degradation rates present a highly adaptable and efficient platform for drug delivery, as demonstrated by the promising performance of the 2Ca-2Alg and Qur@2Ca-2Alg microbeads. The degradation data highlights the ability to fine-tune alginate formulations for specific biomedical uses, balancing release profiles and structural durability. The interaction between quercetin and the alginate matrix, particularly with calcium ions and carboxylate groups, enhances the beads' functionality. Encapsulating quercetin within these beads not only prolongs its therapeutic effects by ensuring sustained release but also protects it from environmental degradation, making this system an effective strategy for enhancing the bioavailability and stability of compounds like quercetin in drug delivery applications.

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